

АНАЛІЗ ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ ПРОТИВІРУСНОГО ЛІКУВАННЯ ХВОРИХ НА
ХРОНІЧНИЙ ГЕПАТИТ С ЗА СХЕМОЮ OBV/PTV/R+DSV±RBV ЗАЛЕЖНО В
ІД НАЯВНОСТІ КОМОРБІДНОЇ НИРКОВОЇ НЕДОСТАТНОСТІ

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIVIRAL TREATMENT OF PATI
ENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS C ACCORDING TO THE SCHEME OBV/PTV
/R+DSV±RBV DEPENDING ON THE PRESENCE OF COMORBID RENAL FAILU
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Introduction. Using of medicine with a direct mechanism of action has expanded the group of patients who can receive treatment for chronic hepatitis C(CHC). Patients without concomitant renal pathology and with comorbid renal insufficiency (RI) stage V, who receive hemodialysis (HD) may receive a 3D-regimen for the treatment of CHC [1,2].

Materials and methods. 101 patients with CHC infected with 1b GT were divided into two groups. Group I -92 patients without concomitant RI, group II

-9 patients with comorbid RI stage V, who received HD. All patients received antiviral therapy (AVT) according to the scheme OBV/PTV/r+DSV±RBV within the State Target Program [3]. Patients were monitored before AVT, at the time of AVT completion, and at 12 weeks to assess sustainable virological response (SVR12).

Group I - 40 men (43.5%) and 52 women (56.5%), aged 27 to 72 years with a median 54.5 [44.5; 61.5]. High viral load (VL) in 56 (60.9%), low VL - in 36 (39.1%) patients. The degree of expressiveness of liver fibrosis (LF): F 0-2 in 48 (57.2%), and F 3-4-44 (47.8%) patients. Group II - 5 (55.6%) men and 4 (44.4%) women aged 31 to 72 years with a median of 47.0 [38.0; 58.0] years. High VL was found in 6 (66.7%), low - in 3 (33.3%). In all patients of group II LF F 0-2 degrees was established.

Results of the research. During the comparison, the groups were represented by sex and age, VL ($p > 0.05$). At the same time, 47.8% of patients in group I had LF F of 3-4 degrees, in patients of group II severe LF was not registered.

It was found that when using the 3D-regimen after 4 weeks and at the end of therapy in group I, the negation of HCV-RNA in the blood occurred in 94.6%, in group II in all patients (100%). SVR12 was formed in 94.6% of patients in group I and 88.9% of patients in group II, with the difference in achieving SVR12 not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

It was found that LF does not affect the frequency of SVR12 ($p > 0.05$) in the treatment scheme of the 3D-regimen.

In group I, already at 4 weeks of AVT, the proportion of patients with normal ALT activity in the serum increased from 33.7% to 76.1% ($p < 0.05$), and at the time of completion to 85.9%, which was more, compared with the beginning of therapy ($p < 0.05$). At the time of SVR12, this figure was 85.2% (46 of 54) patients, which is 2.5 times more than at the beginning of AVT ($p < 0.05$). In patients of group II it was noted that the proportion of patients with normal ALT in serum from 66.7% of patients before AVT to 88.9% of patients at 4 weeks and at the end of therapy ($p > 0.05$). When evaluating SVR12, the proportion of

patients with ALT activity within the norm was 100%. There was no significant difference between the study groups in the frequency of normalization of ALT activity at different times of AVT ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusions. Using of 3D-regimen demonstrates high efficiency for patients with comorbid RI stage V (HD) with a frequency of SVR12 in 88.9% of patients, which is not statistically different from the frequency of SVR12 in 94.6% of patients with CHC without the comorbid pathology ($p > 0.05$). LF does not statistically affect the elimination of the virus during 3D-regimen in patients with CHC, 1b GT ($p > 0.05$).

Literature

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